

Sensitivity Study on Important Parameters for the Hybrid Depletion Method Using Discontinuity Factors

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ABSTRACT

Monte Carlo simulations increasingly become popular as computation capabilities expand. However, in certain areas such as fuel cycle analysis are expensive and require very small time steps or very expensive time integration techniques to suppress nonphysical oscillation. To address these expensive calculations substepping techniques using polynomial extrapolation polynomial interpolation and first order perturbation theory have been developed. Building on this, a hybrid scheme combining a high-fidelity transport solution and a low-fidelity transport solution was developed. It was demonstrated that in a small 2D depletion this hybrid scheme would need a correction factor in the form factors so the homogeneous solution of the low-fidelity solution could capture the heterogeneity of the high-fidelity solution. However, for large systems a correction factor must be able to correct the deviation that occurs not just locally but over the entire system between the homogeneous and heterogenous fluxes. As such the work presented here investigated in a preliminary study on generating reference discontinuity factors (DFs) on the fly as part of the depletion sequence. This generation of DFs enables the low-fidelity transport methods to take advantage of reduced order methods solvers, such as nodal diffusion. Overall, the results demonstrate that hybrid scheme that relies on discontinuity factors would only require one additional computation per macro step.

Keywords: Hybrid Depletion; Equivalence Theory; Monte Carlo; Nodal Diffusion

1. INTRODUCTION

As modern computing has become cheaper and more available it is now more common to use Monte Carlo (MC) codes for the modeling of nuclear systems. MC codes such as Serpent [1], OpenMC [2], and Shift [3] are constantly developed for the express purpose of taking advantage of modern computing. However, even with the advancement of computing, certain applications such as fuel cycle analysis, still prove to be computationally expensive for MC methods. More specifically, for large 3D problems modeled for the entirety of the fuel cycle using fine timesteps, the modeling requirements become prohibitively expensive. It must be pointed out that for small problems, MC-based analysis has been proven useful and efficient for fuel cycle simulations.

The depletion portion of the fuel cycle analysis is traditionally performed using a numerical quasi-static method. Various time integration techniques exist, but they all rely on discretizing the time domain and obtaining the region-wise homogenized flux and microscopic cross sections using a transport code for the beginning (and end-of-step depending on the integration scheme). Then by holding these parameters constant over the time step, the depletion calculation is carried out by solving the Bateman equations to find the isotopic number densities at the end-of-step.

In the quasi-static method, the variation of the homogenized parameters determines the required step size. For larger 3D problems where economical (i.e., coarser) step sizes are desired, it is observed that nonphysical oscillations occurs when the depletion is coupled to MC codes [4,5,6]. Deterministic codes can experience similar oscillatory behavior [7] with some differences on how these unphysical

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behaviors are invoked as there is no stochastic noise within deterministic code. Traditionally this is handled by using smaller step sizes and more recently taking a stochastic implicit Euler approach (SIE) [8]. However, both approaches dramatically increase the cost of depletion by increasing the amount of expensive transport solutions. As such, there is a desire to develop a method of depletion that can update both the spatial and spectral flux without significant increase of cost to the depletion.

To better account for the spatial and spectral changes of the flux, various methods have been developed. A robust solution that accounts for the spectral changes over the time step is to introduce a substepping technique in which a polynomial extrapolation and polynomial interpolation (PE/PI) is applied to the homogenized parameters and fluxes [9,10]. Then to handle the spatial flux, Ref [11] introduced an alternate substepping technique, in which the first order perturbation theory is used to update the spatial distribution of the flux. Both methods were shown to improve on the depletion solution, with PE/PI only improving accuracy and perturbation theory improving stability. Building on the ideas of both these methods, a hybrid depletion scheme in which two transport solutions are used, one using a high-fidelity model and the other a low fidelity model, is used to update the flux spatial and spectrally using first principles [12]. Initial studies of the method focused solely on the spectral aspect of the update by focusing on a pincell [12,13]. Then expanding to a one-dimensional problem, it was found that the hybrid depletion scheme did in fact suppress nonphysical oscillations [14], however the accuracy of the solution was not studied. Simultaneously to these works, the hybrid depletion method was being investigated for 2D system in which it was found that a correction factor was required to obtain accurate results [15]. The correction factor used in Ref [15] is a form factor for the flux, as such for large systems the observed results may break down as the homogeneous and heterogeneous flux deviate from each other more than what the form factor can correct.

In turn for large system another correction factor may be needed. One such correction factor are the discontinuity factors (DFs) of generalized equivalence theory, which has been shown to be resilient to perturbations [16]. This resilience to perturbation is desirable to hybrid depletion as it allows for single calculation for a depletion step without the need to develop a method for updating the DFs between high fidelity transport solutions. Thus, the goal of this paper is to evaluate if the use of DFs is an appropriate solution for the hybrid depletion method. To accomplish this goal, beginning-of-step and end-of-step reference DFs will be evaluated for timesteps of various sizes to observe their changes to temporal perturbation. Following this test a sensitivity study on holding various parameters constant for a depletion step.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Codes

The work presented here uses Serpent [1] as a MC transport solution used a reference and generation of group constants. The depletion of the reference solution was handled externally using the python package PyIsoDep [17], which is capable tracking all isotopes and enforcing equilibrium concentrations. The python package coreCend [18], was used for nodal diffusion and the calculation of reference DFs.

2.2. Hybrid Depletion Sequence using Discontinuity Factors

In previous works the hybrid depletion scheme is envisioned using a macro and micro steps, in which the macro step encapsulates the micro steps between two high fidelity transport solutions and each micro step being each individual depletion step [14]. Throughout the macro step the group constants would be generated with high fidelity solutions and perturbed on the micro step with the depletion calculation. The work here aims to modify the macro step workflow from what is demonstrated in Figure 1 to Figure 2. This modification to the macro step should result in minimal overhead with a quick one-time calculation for reference DFs and enables the ability to use reduced order transport solvers, such as nodal diffusion. In this scheme the reference DFs would rely on the fluxes and surface currents obtained from the high-fidelity transport solution and then used through the entirety of the macro step.

Figure 1. Macro depletion step without use of discontinuity factors.

Figure 2. Macro depletion step with use of discontinuity factors.

Before studying this updated scheme, the feasibility of it is investigated in this paper. The feasibility of this scheme for two tests must be performed. The first test will investigate the validity of using the reference discontinuity factors generated at the beginning-of-the macro step by observing whether the ratio of the DFs at the beginning-of-step and end-of-step have large perturbations or not. Once the first test is verified, the second test will simulate a micro step by using the cross sections generated at the end-of-step and the reference DFs from the beginning-of-step, to observe the deviation of the eigenvalue that would result from this.

To perform this study, a 1D fuel system shown in Figure 3, is depleted from fresh fuel with various step sizes for only a single time step. The step sizes are as follows, 2.5 days, 10 days, 50 days, and 100 days. The left and right sides on the fuel are separated with a 10 cm region of unmoderated fuel and are treated as separate depletion regions. Each of the sides is moderate with water and have the length of 160 cm. For the nodal model each of side regions are split into 4 regions of 40 cm.

Figure 3. 1D UO₂ system with two burnable regions (the green and purple regions) with unmoderated central region (blue).

3. RESULTS

This section will first demonstrate the resilience of DFs to effects of depleting burnable materials. This demonstration will establish that DFs only need to be generated once per macro step. After the demonstration a sensitivity study on various parameters to determine what is required for hybrid depletion sequence. The first test demonstrates the need for DFs in the hybrid depletion sequence and following tests will demonstrate which parameters will require predictor corrector sequence to be applied on the macro step.

3.1. Effect of Time Step Size on Discontinuity Factors

Figure 4 shows the DF ratio for each node for the end-of-step using different step sizes. It is clear that the DF ratio for the left and right side of the center node roughly remains constant for different step sizes, demonstrating that DFs are truly resistant to perturbation caused by depletion and represent a true discontinuity. However, the DF ratio within the moderated fuel regions do deviate significantly as the time steps increase, though this may be an artifact of the statistics not being enough to fully converge on surface parameters. This would suggest that there exists a limit to the step size of which using the beginning-of-step DF would be valid, which is expected as multiple macro depletion steps would be required for the hybrid depletion scheme.

Figure 4. Discontinuity factor ratio (East/West), left: fast, right: thermal.

3.2. Verification of Discontinuity Factors in Hybrid Depletion

In this section the verification of the proposed methodology in Figure 2 is tested alongside sensitivity of which group constants can be held constant for the macro step. The reason for the sensitivity study is that the group constants (besides the DFs) must be generated by the high-fidelity transport solution and perturbed during the depletion step. However, some group constants like the diffusion coefficient and the scattering probabilities are nontrivial to perturb, and as such it would be ideal to keep them constant over the macro step if possible.

Table I and Table II show the deviation of the eigenvalue and power share of coreCend from Serpent, respectively. The cases looked at are as follows, a depletion step only using group constants and no DFs ($\Delta\rho_{no\ corr}$), a depletion step using beginning-of-step DFs ($\Delta\rho_{DF}$), a depletion step using beginning-of-step DFs and diffusion coefficients ($\Delta\rho_{DF+D}$), and a depletion step using beginning-of-step DFs, diffusion coefficients, and scattering probabilities ($\Delta\rho_{DF+D+P_S}$) -the scattering cross section is updated. Looking first at the case where no DFs were used, it is apparent that without DFs there is no possibility of recreating the solution looking at the reactivity deviation. However, the power share of the entire left is preserved, which may be due to the fact that the system is symmetrical. Then looking at the case where the DFs are used from the beginning-of-step demonstrate that DFs have little effect for the power share and eigenvalue for moderately large step sizes. This confirms that the scheme proposed in Figure 2 is feasible and potentially the DFs need be calculated once in a macro step, although it can be adapted if a predictor corrector scheme is applied. The next case was the discontinuity factors beginning-of-step demonstrates an improvement over the just using the beginning-of-step DFs. This improvement suggests that on top of using the beginning-of-step DFs, the diffusion coefficients from the beginning-of-step, would enable larger time steps. Lastly, now holding the scattering probability constant demonstrates an increase in the deviation from the Monte Carlo results and only produces accurate results for time steps smaller than just using DFs from the beginning-of-step. This suggests that to accurately capture the high fidelity results a predictor corrector scheme needs to be applied to the scattering probabilities on top of the microscopic cross sections, for macro step.

Table I. Deviation of Nodal Diffusion from Serpent Reactivity.

Δt (Days)	Serpent k_{eff}	$\Delta\rho_{no\ corr}$ (pcm)	$\Delta\rho_{DF}$ (pcm)	$\Delta\rho_{DF+D}$ (pcm)	$\Delta\rho_{DF+D+P_S}$ (pcm)
2.5	1.23966	185.2	40.8	20.6	56.6
10	1.21591	188.2	16.5	-1.9	49.3
50	1.10612	339.4	-18.0	8.8	222.5
100	1.00113	572.2	-106.2	11.9	306.8

Table II. Deviation of Nodal Diffusion from Serpent Power Share of the Left Side.

Δt (Days)	Serpent Power (left assembly)	%Difference <i>no corr</i>	% Difference <i>DF</i>	%Difference <i>DF + D</i>	%Difference <i>DF + D + P_S</i>
2.5	49.21	0.73	0.91	0.85	1.11
10	51.42	1.14	1.91	2.14	2.05
50	53.18	-2.51	-1.87	-1.93	-2.02
100	52.16	-0.69	-0.26	-0.39	-0.44

4. CONCLUSIONS

As computational capabilities continue to expand, enabling high-fidelity modeling, Monte Carlo simulations are becoming increasingly popular. However, in certain areas such as fuel cycle analysis MC are still quite expensive, especially for large 3D problems, in which very small time steps or very expensive time integration techniques must be used. To address these expensive calculations substepping techniques using polynomial extrapolation polynomial interpolation and first order

perturbation theory have been developed in the past. More recently, a hybrid scheme combining a high-fidelity transport solution and a low-fidelity transport solution was developed.

Previous work showed that this hybrid scheme can produce accurate results and is capable of suppressing nonphysical oscillations. In addition, it was shown that in a small 2D depletion this hybrid scheme would need a correction factor in the form factors so the homogeneous solution of the low-fidelity solution could capture the heterogeneity of the high-fidelity solution. However, for large systems a correction factor must be able to correct the deviation that occurs not just locally over the entire system between the homogeneous and heterogenous fluxes. As such, the work presented here conducted preliminary investigations on generating reference discontinuity factors (DFs) on the fly as part of the depletion sequence. This generation of DFs enables the low-fidelity transport methods to take advantage of reduced order methods solvers, such as nodal diffusion. Overall, the results demonstrate that hybrid scheme that relies on discontinuity factors would only require one additional computation per macro step even in predictor corrector scheme.

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